

APPENDIX

A. PROOF OF PROPOSITION 1

Chang (2020) develops the doubly robust estimator for repeated outcomes in the 2x2 case based on the following score function:

$$\psi(D_i, \theta_0, \pi_0, p, \ell) = \frac{Y_t - Y_g}{\pi_0} \frac{D - p(X)}{1 - p(X)} - \theta_0 - \frac{D - p(X)}{\pi_0[1 - p(X)]} \ell(X)$$

where $D_i \equiv [Y_{i,t}, Y_{i,g}, D, X]$ for repeated outcomes data, $D \in \{0, 1\}$ is a binary treatment indicator, $\pi_0 = P(D = 1)$, $p(X) = P(D = 1|X)$ and $\ell(X) = E[Y_t - Y_g | D = 0, X]$. This yields the estimator:

$$(A.1) \quad \begin{aligned} E \left[\frac{Y_t - Y_g}{\pi_0} \frac{D - p(X)}{1 - p(X)} - \theta_0 - \frac{D - p(X)}{\pi_0[1 - p(X)]} \ell(X) \right] &= 0 \\ E \left[\frac{(Y_t - Y_g)[D - p(X)]}{\pi_0[1 - p(X)]} - \frac{[D - p(X)]\ell(X)}{\pi_0[1 - p(X)]} \right] &= \theta_0 \\ E \left[\frac{D - p(X)}{\pi_0[1 - p(X)]} [Y_t - Y_g - \ell(X)] \right] &= \theta_0 \end{aligned}$$

We now compare this formulation (A.1) to the estimators in (1) and (2) from the main text and show they are mathematically identical.

1. Never treated

Following Callaway and Sant'Anna (2021), define:

$$E \left[\frac{p_g(X)C}{1 - p_g(X)} \right] = E[G_g] = \pi_g$$

where π_g represents the probability of being in group g . Then, the ATT estimator in (1) can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} ATT^{nt}(g, t) &= E \left[\left(\frac{G_g}{\pi_g} - \frac{p_g(X)C}{1 - p_g(X)} \cdot \frac{1}{\pi_g} \right) [Y_t - Y_g - \ell_{g,t}^{nt}(X)] \right] \\ &= E \left[\frac{1}{\pi_g} \left(G_g - \frac{p_g(X)C}{1 - p_g(X)} \right) [Y_t - Y_g - \ell_{g,t}^{nt}(X)] \right] \\ &= E \left[\frac{G_g - G_g p_g(\mathbf{X}) - p_g(X)C}{\pi_g[1 - p_g(X)]} [Y_t - Y_g - \ell_{g,t}^{nt}(X)] \right] \\ &= E \left[\frac{G_g - p_g(\mathbf{X})\omega(g)}{\pi_g[1 - p_g(X)]} [Y_t - Y_g - \ell_{g,t}^{nt}(X)] \right] \end{aligned}$$

with corresponding influence function

$$\psi^{nt} = \frac{Y_t - Y_g}{\pi_g} \frac{G_g - p_g(X)\omega(g)}{1 - p_g(X)} - \theta_{g,t}^0 - \frac{G_g - p_g(X)\omega(g)}{\pi_g[1 - p_g(X)]} \ell_{g,t}^{nt}(X)$$

where $\omega(g) = G_g + C$. The key insight is that Chang's binary treatment indicator D in the two-period case corresponds to group membership G_g in the staggered adoption framework, while the never-treated indicator C plays the role of the control group indicator $(1 - D)$. The generalized propensity score $p_g(X)$ extends the simple propensity score $p(X)$ to account for treatment

timing. Despite these extensions, the fundamental structure of the estimator remains unchanged: it compares treated and control units while adjusting for covariates through both inverse probability weighting and outcome regression.

To complete the equivalence, we examine two specific cases. For $G_g = 1$ and $t \geq g$ such that $C = 0$, we have $\omega(g) = 1$ and:

$$(A.2) \quad ATT^{nt}(g, t) = E \left[\frac{1 - p_g(X)}{\pi_g[1 - p_g(X)]} [Y_t - Y_g - \ell_{g,t}^{nt}(X)] \right]$$

Conversely, when $G_g = 0$ and consequently $C = 1$ and $\omega(g) = 1$:

$$(A.3) \quad ATT^{nt}(g, t) = E \left[\frac{-p_g(X)}{\pi_g[1 - p_g(X)]} [Y_t - Y_g - \ell_{g,t}^{nt}(X)] \right]$$

These two cases correspond exactly to the treated and control states in Chang (2020) two-period framework. (A.2) captures the contribution of treated units ($G_g = 1$), analogous to $D = 1$ in Chang (2020) setup. (A.3) represents the contribution of never-treated units ($C = 1$), corresponding to $D = 0$ in the two-period case. When combined, they yield the same doubly robust structure as (A.1), demonstrating that Callaway and Sant'Anna (2021) never-treated estimator is a multiple-period generalization of Chang (2020) estimator.

2. Not yet treated

For the not-yet-treated case, recall from Callaway and Sant'Anna (2021) that:

$$E \left[\frac{p_{g,t}(X)(1 - D_t)(1 - G_g)}{1 - p_{g,t}(X)} \right] = E[G_g] = \pi_g$$

Then, the ATT estimator in equation (2) can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} ATT^{nyt}(g, t) &= E \left[\left(\frac{G_g}{\pi_g} - \frac{p_{g,t}(X)(1 - D_t)(1 - G_g)}{1 - p_{g,t}(X)} \cdot \frac{1}{\pi_g} \right) [Y_t - Y_g - \ell_{g,t}^{nyt}(X)] \right] \\ &= E \left[\frac{1}{\pi_g} \left(G_g - \frac{p_{g,t}(X)(1 - D_t)(1 - G_g)}{1 - p_{g,t}(X)} \right) [Y_t - Y_g - \ell_{g,t}^{nyt}(X)] \right] \\ &= E \left[\left(\frac{G_g - G_g p_{g,t}(X) - p_{g,t}(X)(1 - D_t)(1 - G_g)}{\pi_g[1 - p_{g,t}(X)]} \right) [Y_t - Y_g - \ell_{g,t}^{nyt}(X)] \right] \\ &= E \left[\left(\frac{G_g - G_g p_{g,t}(X) - p_{g,t}(X)(1 - D_t)(1 - G_g)}{\pi_g[1 - p_{g,t}(X)]} \right) [Y_t - Y_g - \ell_{g,t}^{nyt}(X)] \right] \\ &= E \left[\left(\frac{G_g - p_{g,t}(X)\omega(g, t)}{\pi_g[1 - p_{g,t}(X)]} \right) [Y_t - Y_g - \ell_{g,t}^{nyt}(X)] \right] \end{aligned}$$

with corresponding influence function

$$\psi^{nyt} = \frac{Y_t - Y_g}{\pi_g} \frac{G_g - p_{g,t}(X)\omega(g, t)}{1 - p_{g,t}(X)} - \theta_{g,t}^0 - \frac{G_g - p_{g,t}(X)\omega(g, t)}{\pi_g[1 - p_{g,t}(X)]} \ell_{g,t}^{nyt}(X)$$

where $\omega(t, g) = 1 - D_t + D_t G_g$ captures the time-varying nature of the control group. For $G_g = 1$ and $t = g$ such that $D_t = 1$ for all $t \in \{g, \dots, T\}$, we have $\omega(t, g) = 1$ and:

$$(A.4) \quad ATT^{nyt}(g, t) = E \left[\frac{1 - p_{g,t}(X)}{\pi_g[1 - p_{g,t}(X)]} [Y_t - Y_g - \ell_{g,t}^{nyt}(X)] \right]$$

This result holds for all $t \geq g$. Conversely, for $G_g = 0$ and $t < g$ such that $D_t = 0$ for all $t \in \{1, \dots, g-1\}$, we have $\omega(t, g) = 1$ and:

$$(A.5) \quad ATT^{nyt}(g, t) = E \left[\frac{-p_{g,t}(X)}{\pi_g[1 - p_{g,t}(X)]} [Y_t - Y_g - \ell_{g,t}^{nyt}(X)] \right]$$

The not-yet-treated case extends the equivalence to a dynamic control group that changes over time. The key insight is that $\omega(t, g)$ generalizes the control group indicator to account for units that have not yet received treatment at each time point. Despite this additional complexity, (A.4) and (A.5) demonstrate that the estimator maintains the same doubly robust structure as Chang (2020) original estimator. When $t \geq g$, treated units contribute through (A.4), while not-yet-treated units contribute through (A.5) when $t < g$. Together, these cases exhaust all possible combinations of treatment status and timing in the staggered adoption framework while preserving the fundamental structure of Chang (2020) two-period estimator.

B. PROOF OF PROPOSITION 2

We show the proof for the nyt case. The nt setup is identical. Take the influence function ψ^{nyt} introduced in Appendix A; this can be conveniently rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi^{nyt}(D, \theta_{g,t}^0, \pi_g, \eta_0^{nyt}) &= \frac{Y_t - Y_g}{\pi_g} \left(G_g - \frac{p_{g,t}^0(X) u(g,t)}{1 - p_{g,t}^0(X)} \right) - \theta_{g,t}^0 \\ &\quad - \frac{\ell_{g,t}^{nyt,0}(X)}{\pi_g} \left(G_g - \frac{p_{g,t}^0(X) u(g,t)}{1 - p_{g,t}^0(X)} \right) \end{aligned}$$

where $D \equiv [Y_t, Y_g, G_g, D_t, X]$ and $u(g,t) = (1 - D_t)(1 - G_t)$. Define the directional (Gateaux) derivative of the above equation along $\eta^{nyt} - \eta_0^{nyt} \equiv [\ell_{g,t}^{nyt}(X) - \ell_{g,t}^{nyt,0}(X), p_{g,t}(X) - p_{g,t,0}(X)]$, where $\eta_0^{nyt} \equiv [\ell_{g,t}^{nyt,0}(X), p_{g,t}^0(X)]$ indicates the true unknown values of the infinite-dimensional nuisance parameter $\eta^{nyt} \equiv [\ell_{g,t}^{nyt}(X), p_{g,t}(X)]$, as:

$$(B.1) \quad \partial_r E \left[\psi^{nyt} \left(D, \theta_{g,t}^0, \pi_g, \eta_0^{nyt} + r(\eta^{nyt} - \eta_0^{nyt}) \right) \right]$$

for all $r \in [0, 1)$. The score $\psi^{nyt}(D, \theta_{g,t}^0, \pi_g, \eta_0^{nyt})$ is said to be Neyman orthogonal if the derivative in equation (B.1) vanishes at $r = 0$. To show this, we first derive an explicit expression for equation (B.1). Let $Y_t - Y_g = \Delta$, $\ell_{g,t}^{nyt}(X) - \ell_{g,t}^{nyt,0}(X) = \delta_\ell$, $p_{g,t}(X) - p_{g,t}^0(X) = \delta_p$, and

$$A(r) = \frac{[p_{g,t}^0(X) + r\delta_p] u(g,t)}{1 - [p_{g,t}^0(X) + r\delta_p]}$$

Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_r E \left[\psi^{nyt} \left(D, \theta_{g,t}^0, \pi_g, \eta_0^{nyt} + r(\eta^{nyt} - \eta_0^{nyt}) \right) \right] &= \\ \partial_r E \left[\frac{\Delta}{\pi_g} [G_g - A(r)] - \theta_{g,t}^0 - \frac{(\ell_{g,t}^{nyt,0}(X) + r\delta_\ell)}{\pi_g} [G_g - A(r)] \right] \end{aligned}$$

with:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_r A(r)|_{r=0} &= - \frac{u(g,t)}{[1 - p_{g,t}^0(X)]^2} \delta_p \\ \partial_r [A(r)r\delta_\ell]|_{r=0} &= \left(G_g - \frac{p_{g,t}^0(X) u(g,t)}{1 - p_{g,t}^0(X)} \right) \delta_\ell \end{aligned}$$

Hence:

$$\begin{aligned} & \partial_r E \left[\psi^{nyt} \left(D, \theta_{g,t}^0, \pi_g, \eta_0^{nyt} + r(\eta^{nyt} - \eta_0^{nyt}) \right) \right] \Big|_{r=0} = \\ & E \left[-\frac{\Delta}{\pi_g} \frac{u(g,t)}{[1-p_{g,t}^0(X)]^2} \delta_p - \frac{\ell_{g,t}^{nyt,0}(X)}{\pi_g} \frac{u(g,t)}{[1-p_{g,t}^0(X)]^2} \delta_p - \frac{1}{\pi_g} \left(G_g - \frac{p_{g,t}^0(X)u(g,t)}{1-p_{g,t}^0(X)} \right) \delta_\ell \right] = \\ & -E \left[\frac{u(g,t)}{\pi_g [1-p_{g,t}^0(X)]^2} \delta_p \left(\Delta - \ell_{g,t}^{nyt,0}(X) \right) \right] - E \left[\left(G_g - \frac{p_{g,t}^0(X)u(g,t)}{1-p_{g,t}^0(X)} \right) \delta_\ell \right] \end{aligned}$$

Using the law of iterated expectations, the second expectation can be rewritten as:

$$E \left[\frac{\delta_\ell}{\pi_g [1-p_{g,t}^0(X)]} E[G_g - p_{g,t}^0(X)\omega(g,t)|X] \right]$$

where the second term equals zero because $E[G_g - p_{g,t}^0(X)\omega(g,t)|X] = E[G_g|X] - E[p_{g,t}^0(X)\omega(g,t)|X]$ and $E[G_g|X] = p_{g,t}^0(X)E[\omega(g,t)|X]$, as shown in the proof of Theorem 1 in Callaway and Sant'Anna (2021). Similarly, the first expectation becomes:

$$E \left[\frac{\delta_p}{\pi_g [1-p_{g,t}^0(X)]^2} E[Y_t - Y_g - \ell_{g,t}^{nyt,0}(X)|X, D_t = 0, G_g = 0] \right]$$

since $u(g,t) = 0$ for $D_t = G_g = 1$, $G_g = 1$ or $D_t = 1$. Using the definition of $\ell_{g,t}^{nyt,0}(X) = E[Y_t - Y_g|X, D_t = 0, G_g = 0]$, the former expression also vanishes, yielding

$$\partial_r E \left[\psi^{nyt} \left(D, \theta_{g,t}^0, \pi_g, \eta_0^{nyt} + r(\eta^{nyt} - \eta_0^{nyt}) \right) \right] \Big|_{r=0} = 0.$$

C. FURTHER DETAILS ON THE COVARIATES SELECTED FOR THE EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Table C1 reports the main set of variables used across all farming specifications. This set is then complemented with farming type specific sets (Table C2-C4). The following papers were used as reference for the selection of the covariates: Ait Sidhoum et al. (2023); Arata and Sckokai (2016b); Bertoni et al. (2020b); Chabé-Ferret and Subervie (2013b); Cisilino et al. (2019); Coderoni et al. (2023); Defrancesco et al. (2008); Pascucci et al. (2013); Paulus et al. (2022); Pufahl and Weiss (2009); Stetter et al. (2022b); Uehleke et al. (2022); Vanslebrouck et al. (2002); Waş et al. (2021); Wuepper and Huber (2022); and Zimmermann and Britz (2016).

Table C1: Main set of controls employed in the analysis

Controls	Unit of measure	FADN Code
Family labor	AWU	SE015
Non-family labor	AWU	SE020
Farm size	Ha	SE025
Area of arable land	Ha	SE026
Area of grassland	Ha	SE028
Total output	%	SE131
Total output/input	%	SE132
Farm fixed costs	€	SE270
Income	€	SE410
Buildings	€	SE450
Machinery value	€	SE455
Average farm capital	€	SE510
Total direct payments	€	SE606
Subsidies for LFA	€	SE622
Single farm payments	€	SE631
Altitude	Code	ALTITUDE
LFA and ANC	Code	ANC3
Region	Code	NUTS2
Farm type	Code	TF14

Table C2: Complementary set of controls employed for the COP (TF15) and fieldcrops (TF16) farming type

Controls	Unit of measure	FADN Code
Area rented	Ha	SE030
Area out of production	Ha	SE074
Yield of wheat	%	SE110
Yield of maize	%	SE115
Specific crop costs	€/Ha	SE284
Fertilisers expenditure	€	SE295
Pesticides expenditure	€	SE300
Total subsidies on crops	€	SE610
Shannon diversity index	%	<i>Composite</i>

Table C3: Complementary set of controls employed for the dairy (TF45) and livestock (TF49) farming type

Controls	Unit of measure	FADN Code
Area forage crops	Ha	SE071
Livestock units	LU	SE080
Dairy cows	LU	SE085
Stocking density	LU/Ha	SE120
Milk yield ³	%	SE125
Specific livestock costs	€/LU	SE309
Feed for livestock	€	SE310
Total subsidies on livestock	€	SE615

Table C4: Complementary set of controls employed for the mixed (TF80) farming type

Controls	Unit of measure	FADN Code
Area permanent crops	Ha	SE027
Area rented	Ha	SE030
Area other field crops	Ha	SE041
Area energy crops	Ha	SE042
Area vegetables and flowers	Ha	SE046
Area vineyards	Ha	SE050
Area orchards	Ha	SE055
Area olive groves	Ha	SE060
Area greenhouses	Ha	SE065
Area forage crops	Ha	SE071
Area out of production	Ha	SE074
Livestock units	LU	SE080
Dairy cows	LU	SE085
Pigs	LU	SE100
Poultry	LU	SE105
Yield of wheat	%	SE110
Yield of maize	%	SE115
Stocking density	LU/Ha	SE120
Milk yield	%	SE125
Specific crop costs	€/Ha	SE284
Seeds	€	SE290
Fertilisers expenditure	€	SE295
Pesticides expenditure	€	SE300
Specific livestock costs	€/LU	SE309
Feed for livestock	€	SE310
Total subsidies on crops	€	SE610
Total subsidies on livestock	€	SE615
Shannon diversity index	%	<i>Composite</i>

D. ESTIMATION DETAILS FOR GROUP-TIME AVERAGE TREATMENT EFFECTS

In our main analysis, we deliberately focus on a subset of group-time average treatment effects that can be estimated with greater precision. This selection is motivated by both methodological considerations and the empirical distribution of AES enrollment patterns. As shown in Table 3, AES participation follows a front-loaded pattern, with most farmers enrolling in the early years of the program and participation rates declining exponentially thereafter. This enrollment pattern creates substantial imbalance in the number of treated observations across later treatment timing groups, particularly when disaggregating by farming type.

This imbalance poses estimation challenges for all difference-in-differences estimators, though with different implications. For group-time combinations with very few treated observations (sometimes as few as one treated unit versus thousands of controls), estimating the propensity score becomes problematic regardless of methodology. In our cross-fitting approach, these sparse cells are particularly challenging as we need to fit models on data partitions that may contain extremely few treated observations. While this limitation is somewhat more pronounced when using ML methods, it is important to note that conventional logit-based approaches would also struggle under these conditions or potentially fail entirely.

Beyond estimation concerns, these extremely sparse group-time combinations contribute little to our understanding of overall policy effects, as they represent only a small fraction of farmers receiving environmental payments. Consequently, our focus on more populated group-time combinations allows us to draw conclusions about AES effects that are both more reliably estimated and more representative of the general participant experience.

For completeness and transparency, complete estimation results for all group-time combinations are available upon request. These results should be interpreted with the aforementioned limitations in mind, particularly for later treatment groups with minimal observations.